

Instructions for “Cost_Benefit_Worksheet.xlsm” - making decisions about monitoring the effectiveness of mitigation OR the impacts of development on target species

When opening the worksheet make sure you enable macros, if prompted. You should then see a user form, which is titled, “Cost-Benefit Analysis of Monitoring for Impacts on Target Species”, and you can use this form to enter the parameters for the cost-benefit framework. The outcome of this procedure is a decision on monitoring based on benefits and costs. Below is an explanation of each step of the user form in the worksheet:

Step 1. Enter the estimated probability (value between 0 and 1) that the mitigation measures will be effective OR that the development project will have an impact on the target species (estimated prior to the commencement of monitoring) (parameter = p). If there is no prior information, then set $p = 0.5$ (i.e. 50% probability that the mitigation will be effective OR development will have an impact on the target species).

Step 2. Enter the probability of a Type I error, α (or statistical significance level). In other words, if the real outcome of the project is that the mitigation is effective OR there is an impact on target species then the monitoring will detect that it is not effective OR that there is no impact with probability α (“Alpha” in the worksheet).

Step 3. Enter the value of power here (derived from a power analysis for the proposed monitoring design, which is $1-\beta$).

Step 4. Enter the total cost of monitoring the target species, C_m . This value can be derived from previous/similar monitoring projects.

Step 5. Enter the total cost of additional management actions needed to fix mitigation OR reduce impacts on target species assuming impacts have been detected, C_{fix} . In other words, if the mitigation is found to be ineffective OR if the target species is found to be impacted by the project, then how much would it cost to implement additional management to fix mitigation OR recover the species?

Step 6. Enter the total cost of losing the target species or population locally, C_{loss} , if the monitoring does not detect ineffective mitigation OR the monitoring does not detect an impact. This can be estimated, for example, by the cost of potential future recovery actions that may be required, opportunity costs to the public (i.e. birdwatching/tourism revenue), and/or other ecosystem service values.

Step 7. Enter the probability additional management is implemented given the mitigation OR impact of the project is found to be unacceptable. The value of q can be between 0 and 1. If there is no link between monitoring outcomes and management, then $q = 0$ and if there is a mandatory link between monitoring outcomes and management then $q = 1$.

Step 8. Push the “Enter Data” button once you have entered all values in Steps 1-7. This will populate the cells in the worksheet, which can be saved for later, if needed. Just make sure the cells are reset (push the “Reset” button) if you conduct future analyses (or “Save As” in the worksheet).

Steps 9-10. Once you have entered the data from Step 8, push the “Calculate” button, which will take all of the values you have entered in Steps 1-7 and produce an expected value of not monitoring, which is then compared against the cost of monitoring. The “Monitoring Decision” text box will declare the outcome of the worksheet (i.e. a decision for monitoring).

Reset. The Reset button will clear the form and the corresponding Excel worksheet.

Quit. The Quit button will close the form and take you to the Excel worksheet.